

COMPETENCY-BASED APPROACH IN TEACHING PRESCHOOL CHILDREN

Yunusov I.K.

Andijan State Pedagogical Institute, Department of preschool mathematics, Acting associate
Professor

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Abstract. *In this article, the competences of child's developmental spheres, the basic competences of the preschool age (6-7 years old) child, and the competency-based approach to education of preschool children are revealed.*

Keywords: *child, developmental competencies, physical development, formation of a healthy lifestyle, social-emotional development, speech, communication, reading and writing skills.*

Preschool education is one of the most important stages for the personal and social development of the child. The intellectual, socio-emotional and physical development of the child during this period acts as a preparation for further educational stages. Therefore, new educational programs and state standards are being introduced in the Republic of Uzbekistan based on a competency-based approach in the field of preschool education.

State educational standards are aimed at the formation of competencies in children in various areas, which will help children not only acquire knowledge and skills, but also develop the ability to apply them in practice.

Preschool education serves as the basis for the development of child's basic competencies. It develops in the later stages of education, as well as throughout its life. The public curriculum is based on a competency-based approach. It is aimed at the development of competencies that are formed in different types of children's activities in the process of preschool education and upbringing.

Competence is a set of knowledge, skills, qualifications and values of a child. A child with competence can mobilize and apply his knowledge, skills and qualifications in a particular situation, achieve his goal and solve age-appropriate tasks at each stage of development.

A competency-based approach in teaching preschool children involves the formation of the ability of children to effectively respond to cognitive needs, problems and opportunities, the development of moral standards and values, communication with other people, the formation of a concept of personal -"I". The development of competencies in preschool education allows children to gain self-confidence and form independent thinking skills. This approach requires educators to work individually with each child, taking into account his needs and abilities.

The government of the Republic of Uzbekistan has developed a five-year state program for the development of preschool education in the Republic and a road map in order to expand the coverage of early and preschool children with quality preschool education.[3] The Ministry of preschool education was established to carry out state tasks for the development of preschool education.

A competency-based approach in teaching preschool children provides for the preparation of the growing child's personality for life, the preparation for the formation of methods of activity necessary for solving vital issues, associated with the assimilation of moral norms and values,

communication with other people, the construction of the image of “I”. Initial important competencies require the holistic development of the child as a subject of activity and morality. Competence is a set of knowledge, skills, qualifications and values of a child. Initial competencies, regardless of the area of development, serve as the basis for the formation of child's personality.

Competencies is a multidirectional concept that manifests a set of knowledge, skills, valuable guidance and behavioral skills that condition the successful study and development of the child in the preschool education unit, as well as his commitment to the continuation of his education in the 1st grade of elementary school.[6] The structural elements of knowledge of competencies is the volume of information that a person has. In pedagogy, knowledge is the result of the process of activity of the study of being, which is expressed in the corresponding forms of perception, understanding, thought in the human mind. Values are the general confidence of a person in the goals he wants, which he must achieve in life. They motivate actions, and also serve as guiding principles in solving the issue of how to act.

Values provide criteria for evaluating the actions of both oneself and others, for reasoning thoughts, positions and behavior, for making decisions in alternative options, in seeking to plan and influence the behavior of other people. In pedagogy: skill is an intermediate stage in mastering new methods of action, based on knowledge. Skills are automated components that are generated in the process of performing conscious actions. Practical skill is the ability to solve a concrete issue or apply it to achieve a goal.

The basic competences of young children in preschool age of 6-7.

1. Communicative competence

The importance of developing communication skills in children is great. The child learns to express his opinion in various situations, to communicate correctly with peers and adults. This competence teaches the child to adapt to the social environment and work in a team.

2. Game competence

Play is the main activity of the child. In the process of play, the child shows creativity and initiative, learns various social roles and practices adaptation to life situations.

3. Socio-emotional competence

The child must learn to control his feelings and understand the feelings of others. Socio-emotional development helps the child develop empathy, cooperation and solidarity skills.

4. Cognitive competence

The child's interest in knowledge motivates him to acquire new knowledge. This competence is aimed at developing the thinking of the child and the formation of independent learning skills.

5. Competence in physical development and a healthy lifestyle

The child strengthens his health through movement activities and forms a healthy lifestyle. This competence serves to prepare the child for an active lifestyle.

6. Creative competence

By developing the child's creative potential, he learns to advance new ideas in various situations and solve problems with a creative approach.

What educators should know about basic competencies:

- basic competencies cover knowledge, skills, relationships and valuable guidance;
- basic competencies require educators and child educators to consider children's readiness, their desires, as well as their opportunities and abilities to study;

- basic competencies are collaborative, “work” or “act” together, and influence each other;
- basic competencies strengthen the possibilities and abilities of children to participate in world affairs now and here, instead of preparing them to participate in world affairs at some point in the future;

- basic competencies require educators not only to feel that children are studying and developing, but also to feel how they are studying and how capable they are in the future; [5]

- basic competencies is not only a new name for basic skills and abilities. They also include how these skills are related to knowledge, attitudes, values, and also indicate how these skills are used, launched in mutual actions with others in different situations;

- basic competencies are intended not only for young children, they must be mastered by all - leaders, parents, educators, members of the local community;

- basic competencies help young children to gain self-confidence, to be actively involved throughout life, to read and learn;

- it is necessary that basic competencies are attached to learning process in each area of development;

- basic competencies are developed using effective pedagogy.

The importance of a competency-based approach in the pedagogical process. A competency-based approach facilitates the process of personal development and adaptation to society for children in preschool education. The main task of the educator is to develop independent reading, thinking and decision – making skills in children. In this process, educators use interactive techniques, didactic games and creative activities to develop the child's abilities.

As a result of the reforms adopted by the state in the education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan, great attention is paid to the development of preschool education. In particular, in preschool educational institutions, special educational programs for educators are being developed and new pedagogical technologies are being introduced into practice.

The achievements of the child in the areas of development are completed by pedagogues:- the map of monitoring the development of the child, which is completed three times (including the period from 3 to 7 years), as well as the map of the child's readiness for school of 6-7 years is also completed. This map represents the expected results in terms of competencies of the five areas of bolarivocation according to the state program.

A competency-based approach in the education of preschool children sets the stage for their formation as individuals and their successful development in the future. The competency - based educational process helps children develop skills to apply their knowledge and skills in real-life situations, realize their personal goals, and adhere to moral standards. This approach requires educators to provide education taking into account the individual characteristics and needs of each child.

Through the development of competencies, the child learns not only to master knowledge and skills, but also to actively participate in social life, build self-confidence and be open to new experiences. It is for this purpose that state programs and standards aimed at the development of preschool education in the Republic of Uzbekistan. Also, a competency-based approach forms an important part of the preparatory process for school, since children will be able to successfully study in the primary education with the help of these competencies.

In general, the competency-based approach in preschool education is a modern and effective method that promotes the comprehensive development of children. The correct organization and

implementation of this approach will create a solid foundation for the successful development of the future generation in every possible way.

Recommendations:

1. Educators should introduce techniques based on a competency-based approach to practice widely.

2. It is necessary to develop educational materials suitable for the individual needs and abilities of children.

3. In preschool educational institutions, it is necessary to increase the number of interactive games and creative activities.

4. Training courses should be established for educators on an ongoing basis.

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